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PP 08**BRIDGING GAPS IN PRESSURE ULCER PREVENTION: THE ROLE OF VIGILANT HOME-BASED CARE**

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Introduction: Pressure ulcers are a major source of pain, prolonged recovery, and increased healthcare costs in bedbound patients. Although often viewed as an unavoidable complication of immobility, their development can be prevented with timely interventions across different levels of prevention. This case highlights how vigilant community-based care can mitigate such complications.

Case presentation: Mrs. AB, a 78-year-old woman with a history of transient ischaemic attack in 2011, for which she had defaulted treatment, developed left-sided hemiplegia following an ischaemic stroke in November 2024. Due to impaired mobility, she experienced multiple falls and eventually became bedbound. She was hospitalised and evaluated for melaena in June 2025, after which she was discharged for home-based care with a nasogastric (NG) tube and urinary catheter. Her principal caregiver, an unmarried daughter employed as a housemaid, lives with her in her employer's residence, where supportive measures such as an air mattress were provided. Community-based care was delivered via a Public Health Nursing Officer (PHNO), including regular home visits, NG and catheter care, physiotherapy, and caregiver training on repositioning, skin care, and nutrition — all of which helped prevent pressure ulcers during early recovery.

In July 2025, the patient was admitted to hospital for viral fever. Due to limited resources, an air mattress was unavailable, and caregiver presence was restricted. A sacral pressure ulcer was noted post-discharge. However, the community care team responded promptly: wound care was added to the care plan and delivered through the PHNO during home visits. The patient is now recovering well under continued supportive care.

Conclusion: This case illustrates how patients with severe mobility impairments are at high risk of pressure ulcers during hospitalisation. However, it also demonstrates the value of responsive community-based care in early detection and management. Proactive home-based care not only promotes recovery but also reduces caregiver burden and improves patient outcomes.

Keywords: pressure ulcer prevention, bedbound patients, community-based care

